

**Slovak Society of Chemical Engineering
Institute of Chemical and Environmental Engineering
Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava**

PROCEEDINGS

44th International Conference of the Slovak Society of Chemical Engineering

**Hotel SNP
Demänovská dolina, Low Tatras, Slovakia
May 22–26, 2017**

Editors: Dr. Marek Blahušíak, Dr. Mário Mihaľ

ISBN: 978-80-89597-58-1, EAN: 9788089597581

Václavík, M., Plachá, M., Kočí, P.: Structural characterisation of catalysed particulate filters for automotive exhaust gas treatment, Editors: Blahušíak, M., Mihaľ, M., In *44th International Conference of the Slovak Society of Chemical Engineering*, Demänovská dolina, Slovakia, 724–730, 2017.

Structural characterisation of catalysed particulate filters for automotive exhaust gas treatment

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Keywords: Porous media, reconstruction, DPF, SCR, X-ray tomography.

1. INTRODUCTION

Exhaust gas produced by combustion engines contains both gaseous and solid pollutants. Because their content is limited by emission standards, automobiles need to be equipped with (i) catalytic converters and (ii) particulate filters. Both are in the form of ceramic monoliths consisting of many parallel longitudinal channels. (i) In the case of a catalytic converter, the channels are flow-through and their surface is covered with a catalytically active layer, so called “washcoat”, in which the harmful substances (CO, hydrocarbons and NO_x) are converted to CO₂, water and nitrogen. (ii) The channels of particulate filters are alternately plugged, so the exhaust gas is forced to permeate through macroporous channel walls, filtering out the particulates (scheme in Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: A scheme of the particulate filter operation – exhaust gas is forced to permeate porous walls of the substrate, filtering out the particulates.

A combination of multiple catalytic converters and a particulate filter is often required (e. g. in all Diesel and some gasoline powered engines) – the whole exhaust aftertreatment system is then very space- and cost-demanding. For this reason, effort is made to integrate some of the components in a single device [1-6]: for example, combining two different types of deNO_x catalysts [1], coupling

the deNO_x with oxidation catalyst [2] or particulate filter [3-4], or combination of all these in a single multi-functional unit [5-6]. In such devices, the washcoat consists of multiple layers of different catalysts laid upon each other [1-2], or coated successively along the monolith. In catalysed particulate filters, the washcoat is applied onto/inside macroporous filter walls [3-4].

In the scope of this work, Diesel particulate filters (DPF) containing catalyst for selective reduction of NO_x by ammonia (NH₃-SCR) were studied [3-4]. Catalysed particulate filters need to pass several requirements at the same time – their filtration efficiency and catalytic activity needs to be high, while pressure loss in the filter must be kept minimal, as it limits the engine efficiency. The design of catalysed particulate filters can be aided with thorough structural characterisation – distribution of the washcoat in the walls, porosity of the filter substrate and the washcoat itself, pore size distribution and connectivity are all of interest. In this work, mercury porosimetry, electron microscopy and X-ray tomography (XRT) coupled with mathematical modelling were combined to obtain some of these structural parameters.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PART

2.1 Sample description

The following set of samples was examined in this work – (i) SiC particulate filter and the same filter substrate coated with an SCR catalyst (Cu-zeolite) in two different loadings: (ii) 1.2 g/in³ and (iii) 1.9 g/in³.

The washcoated samples contain pores that can be subdivided into three categories: (i) large macropores in the substrate (approximately 3-50 μm), (ii) smaller macropores in the washcoat – between the catalyst microparticles (50 nm – 3 μm) and (iii) meso-/micro-pores inside the catalyst particles (< 50 nm). Because this study is focused mainly on pressure loss, we concentrated on the large macropores (i) which are the main pathway for gas flow across the wall [4]. Smaller macropores (ii) could not be fully characterised by all techniques used in this work and therefore when they are considered in the analysis, it is specifically mentioned. Transport through the smallest pores (iii) affects the overall efficiency of the catalyst, which can be then limited by diffusion rather than the catalytic activity [7]. They were however irrelevant in the pressure loss study so they are not discussed in this work.

2.2 Characterisation techniques

2.2.1 X-ray microtomography

Small sections were cut out of the filters and trimmed down to a single channel, approximately 8 mm³ of which was then scanned by Xradia MicroXCT 400 machine with the following parameters: source voltage 70 kV, source power 7 W, pixel size 1.14 μm, detector resolution 2016x2016 pixels (binning 1), rotation angle 360°, number of images 1500, exposure time of each image: 7 s, overall scanning time 4.5 hours, temperature 28 °C. The detector and source positions were fixed, while the sample rotated step-wise along the channel orientation. The obtained set of 2D images was reconstructed by special software using corresponding beam hardening, centre shift and other reconstruction parameters.

2.2.2 Mercury porosimetry

Samples (1-2 cm³ in volume) were taken out the filters and placed in measurement cells of a MicroMeritics AutoPore IV 9500 porosimeter. The cells were evacuated and filled with mercury. Subsequently, the pressure was increased step-wise (3 – 60000 psi) and mercury intruded the pores in the sample. Pore diameter can be directly calculated from applied pressure using Washburn equation [8].

2.3 Pressure loss measurement

Pressure loss of the filters was measured in a laboratory apparatus developed for testing catalytic activity of flow-through catalytic converters, which has been fully described elsewhere [9]. The samples were placed in a stainless-steel reactor and sealed. Subsequently, nitrogen was blown through the sample at room temperature and the pressure loss was measured by a differential manometer connected directly in front of and behind the sample. The flow rate corresponding to space velocities reached during vehicle operation (up to 200 000 h⁻¹ [10]) would be too high for the laboratory apparatus, if the whole filters were used – smaller samples were therefore cut out of the filters (69x28x5 mm³ = length, width and height, respectively). Removed channel plugs were recreated using a silicone sealant.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Characterisation

An example of the 3D scan obtained by XRT is presented in Fig. 2. Dimension of the whole scan was approximately 2000x2000x2000 voxels (axes *x*, *y*, *z* in Fig. 2) with the resolution 1.14 μm/voxel. The scans were cropped to approx. 850x200x2000 voxels (as depicted in Fig. 2) to speed up the data processing. Brightness & contrast were adjusted and denoising filters applied. This way, the contrast between the individual phases was enhanced and the images could have been segmented by thresholding – as an example, only the washcoat phase is highlighted in red (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: *Left* – 3D XRT scan of the whole channel, *top right* – a single 2D slice from the cropped image sequence (black = pores, dark grey = SCR catalyst washcoat, light grey = SiC substrate), *bottom right* – the same slice with washcoat phase highlighted in red.

The segmented stacks of 2D images were saved in the form of 3D matrix, where each number represents phase in the corresponding voxel. These digital reconstructions of real porous media can be used for CFD simulations of gas flow and calculation of additional morphological descriptors, such as effective diffusivity, tortuosity, permeability or pore connectivity. In this work, phase volume fractions were calculated – distribution of the phases along axes can be observed and possible inhomogeneities in the washcoat distribution or porous structure of substrate can be found. An average of the 2D pore volume fractions is then equal to sample macroporosity (= pore volume fraction) which was also measured by mercury porosimetry (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: Comparison of pore volume fractions (= macroporosities) measured by XRT and Hg porosimetry.

Overall, the macroporosity decreased with the washcoat loading, as expected. The porosities of bare SiC filter measured by both methods (XRT and Hg porosimetry) were in good agreement. There was however discrepancy in the case of washcoated samples, which increased with the loading of SCR catalyst (Fig. 3). The porosity values obtained by XRT were lower because it did not include the small macropores between the washcoat particles, as they were under the scanning resolution (1.14 $\mu\text{m}/\text{voxel}$), meaning the washcoat phase was regarded as non-porous by XRT. Mercury porosimetry can detect pores in the range of 3 nm – 100 μm (Fig. 4), the washcoat pores were therefore included in the porosity calculation. It is clear from the pore size distribution (Fig. 4) that with increasing loading of the SCR catalyst, the peak describing the large substrate macropores (maximum at 20 μm) becomes less significant, while a secondary peak describing the washcoat pores (100 nm – 3 μm) appears.

Fig. 4: Pore size distribution by mercury porosimetry.

3.2 Pressure loss

The samples are compared in Fig. 5 in terms of pressure loss. The experimental points were fitted by second degree polynomials using least square method. The linear dependency of pressure loss on flow rate in porous media, as described by Darcy’s coefficient [11], must be extended with a quadratic term characterized by Forchheimer’s coefficient, which lumps together inertial effects of the flow through porous medium at high space velocities [12].

As expected, the pressure loss increases with the loading of the washcoat in the filter: bare SiC < SCR/SiC 1.2 g/in³ < SCR/SiC 1.9 g/in³ (Fig. 5). The increase of pressure loss was however non-linear with respect to the amount of the catalytic coating. This trend cannot be explained simply by the decrease of macroporosity – both pore blocking effect of the coated catalytic material and the increase of local velocity in the remaining interconnected pores must be taken into account, which is out of the scope of this paper and is being currently studied.

Fig. 5: Pressure loss in the filter samples as a function of space velocity.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we propose a methodology for characterisation of hierarchically porous media, combining mercury porosimetry with 3D imaging by X-ray tomography, which was applied to catalysed Diesel particulate filters. Porosity values obtained by both techniques were in good agreement. The resolution of 3D scans was sufficient to study large macropores in the filter substrate and washcoat distribution, while mercury porosimetry was used to study also the internal structure of washcoat. The digital reconstructions of real porous media from XRT scans can be further used e. g. for CFD simulations of gas flow and calculation of additional morphological descriptors, such as effective diffusivity, tortuosity, permeability or pore connectivity.

Pressure loss of the filters was measured at varying flow rate – as expected, the backpressure increased with washcoat loading. This increase was however not linear and will require a further study and development of predictive mathematical model, employing simulations of gas flow by CFD and Lattice-Boltzmann method. The experimental data will be used to validate these models.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work has been financially supported (i) by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 686086, (ii) by Johnson Matthey, (iii) within the CENTEM project CZ.1.05/2.1.00/03.0088, co-funded by the ERDF as part of the Czech Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports OP RDI programme and, in the follow-up sustainability stage, supported through CENTEM PLUS (LO1402) under the National Sustainability Programme I and (iv) by the Specific University Research (MSMT No 20-SVV/2017).

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